

Excel Forensics - Detecting Activities without Track Changes

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Abstract: Forensic investigations traditionally focus on the file system. Manipulation of Office documents may also be significant. The use of the Track Changes function is one preferred method. Analysis of the Excel format also reveals chronological changes to data. This makes it possible to detect and trace actions.

Keywords: Detect, Excel, Forensic, HTML, HTTP, Microsoft, Office, XML

1. Preface

This paper was written in 2018 as part of a research project at scip AG, Switzerland. It was initially published online at <https://www.scip.ch/en/?labs.20180503> and is available in English and German. Providing our clients with innovative research for the information technology of the future is an essential part of our company culture.

2. Introduction

Forensic investigation of manipulated files traditionally focuses on fragments in the file system. But modern file formats can also contain data that may offer insights into activities and users. During a customer-specific project, we discovered a new approach to this in the case of Excel documents.

3. The case

The customer creates an Excel document in the XLSX format. This file is located on a file server, which means it can be edited by multiple users.

One of these legitimate users has illegitimately manipulated the file content. This has caused damage, requiring us to find out who was behind the malicious manipulation.

4. Forensic investigation

The customer provided us with the file for analysis. Since the malicious manipulation there had been a number of legitimate modifications to the file content. In addition, the illegitimate manipulation was ultimately reversed (overwritten). An intrusion of this sort is not an ideal starting point for a forensic investigation.

4.1. Traditional approach: Track Changes

The traditional approach is to check the data generated when using the *Track Changes* function. This function can be enabled in Excel (and other Office products) to record each change made to the file content in Office. All changes can be viewed, accepted or rejected.

The disadvantage of this approach is that this function must be deliberately enabled. It is not activated by default and can also be disabled by the user at a later stage.

In our case, Track Changes was not enabled, so we were unable to gather any useful data on this level.

4.2. Advanced alternatives: shared strings

Excel documents saved in XLSX format are XML files based on the *XML spreadsheet format* [1] and are packed in a ZIP archive. So when you change the file extension from *.xlsx* to *.zip*, it can be unpacked in the usual way (using *7zip*, for instance). The archive contains individual *files and subdirectories* [2].

Name	Date modified	Type	Size
_rels	14.09.2017 10:38	File folder	
theme	14.09.2017 10:38	File folder	
worksheets	14.09.2017 10:38	File folder	
sharedStrings.xml		XML Document	1 KB
styles.xml		XML Document	2 KB
workbook.xml		XML Document	1 KB

Figure: Content of an XLSX file

The XML documents are stored in the *xl/* subdirectory, which contains a file called *sharedStrings.xml*. This file contains all of the values found at least once in a cell in the Excel document. If they occur multiple times, they can be referenced in the worksheets under *xl/worksheets/*. This referential usage saves resources, much like a relational database.

What is interesting about this file is that the *shared strings* it contains are recorded in *chronological order* [3]. So if the value *Test 1* is entered into a cell and then *Test 2* in another, both of these values will be stored in precisely this order.

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"
standalone="yes"?>
<sst
xmlns="http://schemas.openxmlformats.org/spreadsheetml/2006/main" count="3"
uniqueCount="3"><si><t>The first entry</t>
</si><si><t>The second entry</t></si><si>
<t>The third entry</t></si></sst>
```

This means you can trace the order in which data was entered. Overwritten cells are also replaced in shared strings, and deleted cells are deleted. It is not possible to inject tags, as special characters (e.g. chevrons) are HTML-encoded.

Action in Excel	Effect in sharedStrings.xml
Fill cell	New entry at the end of the list
Overwrite cell	Replace existing entry in the same position
Delete cell	Existing entry deleted without replacement

In this particular case, we were able to use individual data to identify who entered data before and after the malicious manipulation, greatly narrowing down the number of potential culprits.

5. Conclusion

Good forensic investigators have to be creative with the means at their disposal. Modern computer systems offer numerous data sources that can be used for the purposes of analysis. This can be crucial, as the culprits are often unaware that this is possible. That was the case here, where analyzing the circumstances made a major contribution to the progress of the investigations.

6. External Links

[1] <https://msdn.microsoft.com/en-us/library/aa140066%28office.10%29.aspx>

[2] <https://msdn.microsoft.com/en-us/library/office/gg278316.aspx>

[3] <https://stackoverflow.com/questions/46198532/xlsx-forensic-analysis-of-changes/46215074#46215074>